

Effect of chelation on therapeutic potential of drugs : Synthesis and characterization of novel VO^{II}, Fe^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of ornidazole drug and evaluation of their antibacterial activity

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Abstract : Complexes of VO^{II}, Fe^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} transition metal ions with an antibacterial and antiprotozoal drug ornidazole (ONZ) [1-chloro-3-(2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole-1-yl)propane-2-ol] were synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, IR, UV-Vis, magnetic moment, molar conductance, ¹H NMR, thermal and FAB-mass spectra. Analytical data revealed that all the complexes exhibited 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) ratio with coordination number 4, 5 or 6. IR spectra show that ligand (ONZ) is coordinated to the metal ions in a monodentate manner through N donor site of imidazole ring. The thermal behavior of [Cu(ONZ)₂(H₂O)₂Cl₂].2H₂O complex show that the hydrated complexes lose water molecules first, followed by decomposition of ligand molecule in the subsequent steps. Ornidazole (ONZ) drug ligand and its metal complexes were also screened for *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Proteus mirabilis*. Effect of metal ions chelation on antibacterial potential of ornidazole (ONZ) drug has been studied.

Keywords : Ornidazole, spectral characterization, thermal analyses, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

1-Chloro-3-(2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole-1-yl)propan-2-ol is a synthetic 5-nitroimidazole derivative with action similar to metronidazole and tinidazole. It is used in the treatment of susceptible protozoal infection and also as potential antibacterial agent against anaerobes, including bacteroides and clostridium species¹, infections caused by periodontopathic Gram-negative bacteria viz. *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Prevotella intermedia*, *Prevotella melaninogenica* and *Bacteroides forsythus*. It has been investigated for use in Crohn's disease after bowel resection. The antimicrobial activity of ornidazole is due to the reduction of the nitro group to a more reactive amine that attacks microbial DNA; it brings the loss of helical structure of DNA and subsequent DNA breakage thus inhibiting further synthesis and causing degradation of existing DNA²⁻⁵. To tailor the activity of ornidazole, life essential transition metals (VO^{II}, Fe^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}) were introduced into the molecular structure of ornidazole by the reaction of appropriate metal precursor. The ornidazole has potential to bind the metal

ion through imidazole nitrogen atom. Such binding are likely to trigger and monitor the biological activity.

Structure of ligand (ornidazole)

Results and discussion

The analytical and physical data of metal complexes are presented in Table 1. All the complexes are non-hygroscopic solids and soluble in alcohols, DMF and DMSO. The analytical and spectroscopic data showed that all the complexes exhibit 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry.

¹H NMR studies :

In the ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand and diamagnetic

Table 1. Analytical, physical and IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) ornidazole ligand and its complexes

Compd./ Formulae	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%):				IR Frequency of ligand and metal complexes (cm ⁻¹)					Λ_m^a
		Found (Calcd.)				$\nu(\text{C-N})$	$\nu(\text{O-H})$	$\nu(\text{C-O})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	(H ₂ O)	
Mol. wt. (Colour)		C	H	N	M						
C ₇ H ₁₀ N ₃ O ₃ Cl (ONZ)	-	37.98	4.30	18.89	-	1469	3311	1273	-	-	-
219 (Cream)		(38.02)	(4.50)	(19.01)							
[Cu(ONZ) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂].2H ₂ O	84.5	26.34	4.15	13.54	10.01	1480	3314	1274	493	3498,	30
646 (Sky blue)		(26.01)	(4.37)	(13.01)	(9.84)					679	
[Zn(ONZ) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ .H ₂ O	79.5	27.05	4.01	13.03	9.98	1485	3312	1273	474	3456,	125
629 (Cream crystal)		(26.79)	(4.16)	(13.35)	(10.19)					677	
[Fe(ONZ) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂ SO ₄].H ₂ O	68.3	25.89	3.94	12.78	8.54	1475	3311	1269	478	3234,	37
645 (Golden brown)		(26.05)	(4.06)	(13.02)	(8.66)					707	
[VO(ONZ) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄ .2H ₂ O	67.5	25.52	3.72	12.43	7.80	1479	3314	1269	489	3261,	123
674 (Parrot green)		(24.94)	(4.19)	(12.46)	(7.55)					707	

^a $\Lambda_m = (\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1})$

Zn^{II} complex, signal due to the alcoholic OH proton of the free ligand at δ 3.980 ppm, remain unaltered after complexation, confirming the non-involvement of alcoholic group in chelation. The spectra show three proton doublets at 2.453 and 2.502 ppm due to methyl group in ligand and Zn^{II} complex, respectively. The proton of HC-N group of imidazole ring (ligand) at δ 8.030 ppm has shifted to higher field at δ 8.005 ppm, confirming the involvement of HC-N group of imidazole (nitrogen) in coordination with the metal ions. All these data put together clearly suggest that the ligand coordinate to metal ion in monodentate manner^{6,7}.

FAB-mass spectra :

The FAB-mass spectra of [Zn(ONZ)₂(H₂O)₂]Cl₂.H₂O complex exhibited the molecular ion (M⁺) peak at m/z 630 suggesting its monomeric nature⁸.

IR spectra :

The IR spectrum of free ligand was compared with that of the metal complexes in order to confirm the coordination of ligand to metal. The $\nu(\text{C-N})$ band of imidazole ring appears at 1469 cm⁻¹ in the ligand. In complexes this band appears in the range 1475–1485 cm⁻¹, confirming that $\nu(\text{C-N})$ of ornidazole ligand is involved in complexation⁹. The spectrum of the free ligand shows bands at 3311, 1384 and 1273 cm⁻¹, due to the stretching and deformation of the $\nu(\text{O-H})$ and $\nu(\text{C-O})$ of alcoholic group. These absorptions remain unaltered in all metal complexes, confirming the non-involvement of the alcoholic group in chelation with all metal complexes. The

broad bands around 3234–3498 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of all the complexes, suggest the presence of water molecules in the complexes. A medium intensity band at 677–707 cm⁻¹ in all complexes is assigned to rocking mode of coordinated water molecules. Some new bands of medium intensity at 474–493 cm⁻¹ in all complexes give inference of $\nu(\text{M-N})$ mode. A characteristic non-ligand band at 974 cm⁻¹ in VO^{II} complex has been assigned to $\nu(\text{V=O})$ vibration. The presence of an ionic sulphate group in Fe^{II} and VO^{II} complexes has been confirmed by the appearance of the three bands at 1103, 999, 597 cm⁻¹ and 1111, 1041, 592 cm⁻¹ respectively^{10,11}.

Magnetic measurements and electronic spectra :

The VO^{II} complex exhibits two bands at 14084 and 23809 cm⁻¹, which have tentatively been assigned to ²B₂-²E (v₁) and ²B₂-²A₁ (v₂) transitions. On the basis of electronic spectral data the square pyramidal geometry has been suggested for the VO^{II} complex. The value of the magnetic moment for this complex is 1.76 B.M., indicating presence of one unpaired electron. The electronic spectrum of Fe^{II} complex consist of one low intensity band at 21978 cm⁻¹, arising from a ⁵T_{2g}-⁵E_g transition. The value of magnetic moment is 5.14 B.M., which corresponds to octahedral geometry. The spectrum of Cu^{II} complex consists of a broad band at 12820–16393 cm⁻¹, assignable to ²E_g-²T_{2g} transition. The electronic spectral value suggested octahedral geometry for Cu^{II} complex. The value of magnetic moment is 1.88 B.M. indicating presence of one unpaired electron in complex^{12,13}.

Note

Thermal analyses :

A thermal analysis of Cu^{II} complex showed that it was stable upto $60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Two lattice water molecules were lost around temperature upto $94\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Above $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, weight loss has been observed upto $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which correspond to two coordinated water molecules. A small endothermic peak at $93\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the DTA curve of Cu^{II} complex suggested some change in the composition of the complex. A gradual weight loss between $200\text{--}224\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, corresponded to release of chloride ions from the metal complex. In this stage the DTA curve showed an exothermic peak at $216\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, whereas the corresponding DTG curve showed peak at $217\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The remaining step of decomposition within the temperature range $225\text{--}400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, corresponds to the removal of ligand part (Remaining wt.% obsd./calcd. $48.95/48.91$). In this step, DTA and DTG peaks does not appear. The subsequent step ($400\text{--}800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) corresponds to the decomposition of the organic ligand, leaving metal oxide as residue¹⁴.

Antibacterial activity :

The synthesized metal complexes were screened for *in vitro* antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* and *P. mirabilis* species by Well diffusion method using agar as nutrient medium. Results of compounds are given in Table 2. For *E. coli* and *P. mirabilis* microorganisms, the biological activity of VO^{II} , Fe^{II} and Zn^{II} , complexes is higher than that of the ligand but less than streptomycin, while for Cu^{II} complex, the biological activity of complexes is less than that of ligand. On the other hand, for *S. aureus*, the biological activity of Fe^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes is higher than that of the ligand and streptomycin, and nearly the same as the ligand for VO^{II} complex. It was found that incorporation of metal increase/affect the activity of ornidazole (Fig. 1)^{15,16}.

Experimental

Materials :

All the used chemicals and metal salts were of A.R. grade. Ornidazole was obtained as a gift sample and was used as such.

Instrumentation :

Elemental analysis of the ligand and complexes were performed micro-analytically on Elemental Vario EL III

Fig. 1. Antibacterial activity of ligand (ornidazole) and its metal complexes against *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *P. mirabilis*.

Carbo Erba 1108 analyzer. The molar conductance of the complexes were determined by preparing (10^{-3} M) solu-

tions of the complexes in methanol at room temperature and measured on Elico-CM82 conductivity Bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on a Gouy balance at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO solution on Perkin-Lambda-2B-spectrophotometer. IR spectra of ligand and complexes were recorded on Perkin-Elmer RX-I spectrophotometer as KBr pellets. ^1H NMR spectra of ligand and Zn complex were recorded in DMSO on JEOL AL300 FTNMR spectrophotometer. FAB-mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA 6000 Mass spectrometer using argon/xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and the spectra were recorded at room temperature. Thermal studies of the complex were carried out on Perkin-Elmer Thermal Analyzer between room temperature to 800 °C.

Preparation of metal complexes :

VO^{II} , Fe^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes were prepared by refluxing methanolic solution of metal salts with the ligand in 1 : 2 ratio, on a water bath for about 5–7 h. A solid product appeared on standing and cooling the refluxate. It was filtered off, recrystallized twice with ethanol, finally washed with petroleum ether, and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 . The progress of the reaction and purity of the product was monitored by TLC using silica gel G.

Biological activity :

Ligand and the metal complexes were screened *in vitro* antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Proteus mirabilis* species by well diffusion method using agar as nutrient medium. Each of the compounds was dissolved in DMSO and the solutions of the concentrations (25, 50 and 100 ppm) were prepared separately. In a typical procedure, a well was made on the agar medium inoculated with microorganism. The well was filled with the test solution using a micropipette and the plate was incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. After incubation, the diameter of the clear zone of inhibition surrounding the sample was taken as a measure of the inhibitory power of the sample against the particular test organism.

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